

A Gap Analysis of Students' Expectations and Perceptions of Service Quality at the Takoradi Technical University

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Abstract

Tertiary education places students as primary consumers and as such, students are conscious of their rights and the gaps between their expectation and perception of service delivery. Not only does this service gap present a quality assurance challenge for educational institutions, it is also likely to contribute to student withdrawal. This study undertaken to determine the quality gap between students' expectations and perceptions of service delivery as well as calculate and measure the score of the five SERVQUAL dimensions. The study adopted both the mixed-method approach. Stratified sampling method was used to select respondents and this was done by putting the entire population into five main strata; comprising five faculties. Five percent (5%) of the second- and third-year students from each faculty were chosen as respondents. The study focused on the dimensions of service quality from students' perspective using Higher National Diploma students at the Takoradi Technical University. The tangibility dimension was found to have a positive gap of approximately 1.32 showing that the institution delivered beyond expectation of its students. The reliability dimension however, showed a negative dimension of 1.03 in service quality which indicates that the University fell short of its service quality dimensions leading to student dissatisfaction. The responsiveness dimension was also found to have service quality level of 1.42 above the expected service quality delivery of 3.14. However, the assurance dimension recorded just a marginal improvement of 0.85 of service quality over the expected service quality of 3.65. Finally, the empathy dimension recorded an expected service quality of 3.02 while the perceived service quality was 4.00. This represented an increase of 0.98 in service quality. After comparing the differences between students' perceptions and expectations, the results showed a positive score, as the student's perception exceeded their expectation. Tangibility and responsiveness dimensions were rated highest, followed by assurance, and then empathy while reliability was rated the least dimension. The results showed that students' expectation of service quality was exceeded thus, presenting a great challenge to the Technical University, to maintain or even improve such dimensions. Management was thus encouraged to make a conscious effort to improve teaching and learning by making available modern teaching equipment for teaching and learning. This will go a long way in meeting the expectations of the students in this regard. Management was also encouraged to continuously measure the Institution's service quality and improve on it.

Keywords: Gap Analysis, Perceptions of Service Quality

Introduction

The strategic success of a service organization depends on the ability of the service provider to enhance its image by consistently meeting or exceeding customers' service expectation. Service organizations now recognize the importance of quality and attempt to exceed the expectations of customers. While the level of perception varies from customer to customer, if service quality increases the value for the customer experience, then one method to obtain this level is through the implementation of a well-coordinated internal mechanisms (Ballantyne et al 1995). These mechanisms must be measured regularly in response to the changes of the environment where the expectation of the stakeholder is becoming higher. The findings of the measurement are very useful to the Technical University administrators as well as the teaching staff to provide plans and solutions for the continuous improvement so that the services and the programmes offered are relevant to students and stakeholders. It is important for educational institutions to be aware of students' needs and expectations, and take steps to identify, and meet those expectations. Students, especially mature age students, whether local or international, expect quality service delivery (Mavondo & Zaman, 2000), It is therefore, important that the services offered by a tertiary educational institution assist students to settle into the academic

environment as smoothly as possible. Quality has thus, become a “major preoccupation” in the higher educational sector, as reported by Wright and O’Neill (2002).

It is vital to regularly measure the performance of service quality from students’ perspective because they are directly involved in the education process. They are regarded consumers as well as the product of educational institutions. Students’ view on all aspects of their educational experiences is essential to monitor the quality of education. The data and information gained would help the service provider and the stakeholder to make judgment about the level of quality in the educational sector (Brennan & Sheh, 2000).

Tertiary education places students as primary consumers and as such, students are conscious of their rights and the gaps between their expectation and perception of service delivery. Not only does this service gap present a quality assurance challenge for educational institutions, it is also likely to contribute to student withdrawal (Darlaston-Jones et al., 2003). Literature shows the benefits of student feedback in tertiary institutions, and it enables management to develop quality assurance programmes to meet the expectations of students as key stakeholders (Harvey, 2001). Takoradi Technical University as an educational institution has all the characteristics of a service industry. Records have shown that the institution has not established a proven and acceptable methodology for evaluating the quality of services they provide except for teaching and learning. There has not been any study on the quality of service delivery particularly from the students’ perspective. Similarly, Takoradi Technical University has not put any mechanism for assessing its service quality and the gap between students’ expectation and perception among students in the institution. The basis of this study is to determine the existence of quality gap (if any) with respect to service delivery at the Takoradi Technical University and make recommendations to assist management to address the concerns of the students.

The study made a gap analysis of students’ satisfaction of service quality at the Takoradi Technical University. The study is focused on Higher National Diploma students at the Takoradi Technical University. It is focused on the dimensions of service quality from students’ perspective. Literature suggests that, there are a wide range of resources available to all students in tertiary institutions to support them in all aspects of their studies. The range of services provided by tertiary institutions include: teaching and learning services, research services, counseling services, medical services, career services, accommodation, clubs and societies (Harvey, 2001). Takoradi Technical University as a tertiary institution provides all the services listed above but for the sake of limitations; the study is focused on the quality of teaching and learning (lecture halls and delivery) and research support (library) services provided by the institution. The goal of the study is to determine the quality gap (if any) between students’ expectations and perceptions of service delivery at Takoradi Technical University. To achieve this goal, the following specific objectives were accomplished; to determine the gap between expectations and perceptions using the gap analysis and to calculate and measure the score of the five SERVQUAL dimensions.

2.0 Outcomes of Service Quality

Customer satisfaction is a revenue and retention building process. The goal of each business transaction is to gain customers and retain them through trust and commitment (Anderson and Narus, 1998). The creation of value and trust affects current marketing strategies which influences the lifetime value of each customer and directly impacts current and future sales. An organization will maximize profit by focusing on the needs of the most valuable customers through line extensions, service, and amenities; this will create a competitive advantage within an industry (Zeithaml et al., 2001). These needs are fulfilled through a service exchange that consists of a psychological contract in which a need is gratified in exchange for money, time, and effort. The level of satisfaction obtained translates into the level of loyalty and the level of satisfaction created significantly impacts the customer defect rate. Service Quality is commonly noted as a critical prerequisite for establishing and sustaining satisfying relationship with valued customers. In this way, the association between service quality and customer satisfaction has emerged as a topic of significant and strategic concern (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). In general, perceived service quality is an antecedent to satisfaction. Thus, a proper

understanding of the antecedents and determinants of customer satisfaction can be seen as to have an extraordinarily high monetary value for service organization in a competitive environment.

2. 1 Gaps Model of service quality

The Gaps Model of service quality has been used since 1990. The Gaps Model was originally developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988). It has been widely used by many researchers when analysing the gaps between customers’ expectations and their perceptions (Parasuraman et al., 1988). The Gaps Model of service quality serves as a conceptual framework for understanding service quality delivery. Based on evidence that service quality as a function of the difference between consumer expectations and perceptions, Parasuraman et al. (1988) conducted an exploratory study in an attempt to establish how consumers evaluate service quality. The study suggested that, regardless of the service or service industry, consumers use the same criteria in evaluating service quality (Zeithaml et al., 2003). Service organisations can use the Gaps Model to identify customer level of dissatisfaction which occurs when actual service delivery does not meet the customers’ expectations of service performance, implied in the company’s communication (Mc Coll et al., 1996). Companies need to close the gap between what customers expect and receive. The central focus of the Gaps Model is the Customer Gap, the difference between customers’ expectations and perceptions. Firms need to close this gap in order to satisfy their customers and build long-term relationships with them (Ziethaml et al., 2003). Figure 2.1 relates to the Gaps Model of Service Quality and highlights the 5 Gaps of service quality identified by Parasuraman et al. (1988). According to Parasuraman et al. (1988), Gap 5 (Customer Gap) is the most important gap to close.

Figure 2.1: SERVQUAL Gap Analysis Model

Source: Grootroos, 2000.

2. 1.1 Gap 1: Not knowing what customers expect

This is the difference between customer expectations of service and the company understanding of those expectations (Ziethaml et al., 2003). This gap occurs when management does not interact directly with customers, or is unwilling to ask about their expectations. Gap 1 could have several causes, such as insufficient use of market research, insufficient upward communication between contact employees and management and too many layers between contact employees. For example, management in tertiary institutions may not understand what students’ expectations are because they do not interact directly with the students or they do not take suggestions from staffs that do interact with students and understand students’ expectations.

To close or minimize Gap 1, it is important for management and employees in the organization to have the authority to change or influence service policies and procedures (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

2. 1.2 Gap 2: Not having the right service quality designs and standards

According to Ziethaml et al. (2003), Gap 2 is the difference between a company's understanding of customer expectations and development of customer-driven service designs and standards. Possible causes of Gap 2 include management believing that customer expectations are unreasonable or unrealistic or management may believe that the degree of variability in the service defies standardization and, therefore, setting standards will not achieve the desired goal.

The gap between management's understanding of customer expectation and the translation of these expectations into service quality depends on a number of factors:

- Management commitment to service quality;
- The extent to which the service role in the company is standardized and routine; and
- Goal setting and the existence of a formal mechanism for setting the quality of service goals (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

To close or minimize Gap 2, management must be committed to improving service quality by developing customer defined service standards to meet customer expectations, designing services without oversimplification, incompleteness or bias. Similarly, Lovelock et al. (2004), suggests that the service provider must design physical evidence to meet customers' expectations. For example, management in a tertiary institution may develop a quality management suggestions program that is designed to meet students' expectations.

2. 1.3 Gap 3: Not delivering to service standards

Gap 3 is the difference between development of customer driven service standards and actual service performance by company employees (Ziethaml et al., 2003). Even when guidelines exist for performing services, quality service delivery is not guaranteed and appropriate resources should be provided to support quality outputs, such as people, systems and technology. The level of service delivery may fall below the expected standard due to ineffective recruitment, poor employee technology job fit, lack of empowerment, perceived control and team work (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

To close Gap 3, Parasuraman et al (1988), suggests that employees should understand the roles they are to play in the company. Employees should have clear goals and objectives concerning the company, they should implement appropriate strategies and obtain regular feedback on their performance (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

Management must recruit the right people for the right job and train them in using technology and purchasing the equipment that will be appropriate to increase employee-technology job fit. Lovelock et al. (2004) adds to Zeithaml et al. (2003) by suggesting that appropriate recognition and reward programmes must be in place to help measure the performance expected from employees and also create team spirit among them. Lovelock et al. (2004) suggests that, by empowering employees to take control of certain areas in the department, they will improve the quality of service provided to customers, minimize time wasted in obtaining authorization and reduce the stress level.

Possible examples of Gap 3 in the context of the University service delivery could be computer illiteracy amongst staff hindering work performance, layers of management that need consultation before services can be performed. Factors contributing to inefficiency are ineffective staff interaction with students and a lack of team work amongst staff.

2. 1.4 Gap 4: When promises do not match performance

Gap 4 is defined as the difference between service delivery and the service provider's external communications. Promises made by a service company through its media advertising, sale increases and other communications may raise customer expectations that serve as the standard against which customers assess service quality (Ziethaml et al., 2003). Gap 4 can occur for the following reasons: over-promising in advertisement or personal selling, inadequate coordination between operations, marketing and difference in policies and procedures across service outlets (Ziethaml et al., 2003).

Gap 4 can be closed by improving service delivery and managing all communications to customers so that inflated promises do not lead to higher expectations. Employees at a Technical University should not promise service that they cannot deliver. If Technical University employees over-promise and they are not able to deliver on such promises, students form a negative perception of service quality at the Technical University.

2. 1.5 Gap 5: The Customer Gap

Parasuraman et al. (1985) identified Gap 5, as the difference between expected service and perceived service, which supported the notion that the key to delivering quality is to meet or exceed customer expectations. Gap 5 is defined as service quality. Parasuraman et al. (1988) argue that gap 5 is the sum total of the preceding four gaps. Thus, if management want to close the gap between perceptions and expectations, it becomes important to design quality management systems to measure service performance against expectations. The other gaps play important roles in the delivery of quality service, Gap 5 which ultimately must be closed if an organization is to succeed in the long-run (Parasuraman et al., 1988). This is illustrated in Figure 3.2 below;

Figure 2.2: Gap 5 – The Customer Gap

Source: Ziethaml et al., 2003.

Source: Ziethaml et al., 2003.

Gap 5, which is the difference between customers' expectation and perception of service quality, is viewed as the most important gap to close in attempting to improve service quality within a service organisation. It was emphasised that Gap 5 forms the basis of the study, investigating students' perceptions of service quality at the Takoradi Technical University.

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted both the mixed-method (Quantitative and Qualitative) and case study approaches. The mixed-method design involved collecting and analyzing the data in succession, first, the quantitative data (numeric) and second, the qualitative data (Creswell, et al., 2003). The quantitative (numeric) data was collected first to find out students' expectations and perceptions of service quality in Takoradi Technical University. The qualitative (text) data was collected and analyzed second in the sequence to help explain, or elaborate on, the quantitative results obtained in the first phase. The rationale for this approach is that the quantitative data and their subsequent analysis provide a general understanding of the research problem (Ivankova, et al., 2006). The qualitative data and their analysis however, refine and explain those statistical results by exploring participants' views in more detail (Ivankova, et al., 2006; Rossman and Wilson 1985).

3.2 Population of the Study

The entire students and academic staff of Takoradi Technical University constituted the population for the study. Available data obtained from the Planning Unit of the Takoradi Technical University indicated that the student enrolment strength is eight thousand nine hundred and six (8906) comprising three thousand, one hundred and seventy two (3172) first year students (2092 males and 1080 females), three thousand one hundred and ninety (3190) second year students, (2146 males and 1044 females), and two thousand, five hundred and forty-four (2544) third year students, (1767 males and 777 females). Codes were used to hide the identity of the students and make categorization easier. The first-year students were omitted as they were new in the system and might therefore be limited in their understanding of service quality in the institution.

3.3 Research Sample and Sampling

Since it was not possible to reach out to every individual in the Technical University, a sample was selected. Stratified sampling method was used to select respondents and this was done by putting the entire population into five main strata; comprising five faculties. Five percent (5%) of the second- and third-year students from each faculty were chosen as respondents. The sample from each was further divided into male and female categories. Simple random sampling technique was then used to select the stipulated number of respondents from each category. The selected respondents were then put together to form sample for the research. The simple random sampling technique was appropriate because it gives each member in the population an equal chance of being selected.

3.4 Research Instrument

A primary data was collected and used for the research. A questionnaire was developed to elicit information on students' expectations and perceptions of service quality with particular reference to Takoradi Technical University. The items were divided into three sections; section A of three items for students, sought information on students' expectations of service quality, section B dealt with students' perceptions of service quality and section C dealt with additional questions to illicit students' general knowledge of service quality.

A semi-structured questionnaire and an interview guide were used for the data collection. Questionnaires were personally administered with the help of research assistants to three hundred and seventeen (317) participants. Questionnaires were used because data collected using questions can be stable, constant and has uniform measure without variation. It also reduces bias caused by the researcher's presentation of issues.

An interview was appropriate for the study since it makes it easier and flexible for the researcher to control the order in which questions are arranged. Again, personal contact enabled the respondents to participate and to provide the needed information.

3.6 Data Analysis Techniques

Out of the 317 questionnaires sent, 188 were retrieved. The quantitative data was analysed with Microsoft Excel and the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) 20.0. The results were presented using descriptive statistics (percentage frequencies, graphs and charts). The qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis. A paired sample z-test was used in computing the differences between the variables.

The Paired sample z-test compares the means of two variables. It computes the difference between two variables for each case, and tests to see if the average difference is significantly different from zero (Archambault, 2000). A z-test was carried out on each of the 30 questions to determine whether the mean rating of perceptions is different from the mean rating of expectations. The paired sample form of the z-test was applied since the same subjects were used to rate both expectation and perception. All questionnaires were numbered serially according to the sequence in which they were received. The responses were quantified and coded on broad data summary sheets to facilitate easy loading unto the computer. The analysis of data allowed the researcher to manipulate information collected during the study in order to assess and evaluate the findings and arrive at some valid, meaningful and relevant conclusions.

4.1. Paired Sample Test and correlation

One of the most common experimental designs is the "pre-post" design and a comparison of variable after taking initial observations and given a trend of time, a repeated experiment is conducted to know the impact of time difference has resulted. A study of this type often consists of two measurements taken on the same subject and at the same time, one to measure based on reality and the other on intuitive. The basic idea is to know if the treatment had no effect, the average difference between the measurements is equal to 0 and the null hypothesis holds. On the other hand, if the treatment did have an effect (intended or unintended!), the average difference is not 0 and the null hypothesis is rejected.

The Paired-Samples Z Test procedure is used to test the hypothesis of no difference between two variables. The data may consist of two measurements taken on the same subject or one measurement taken on a matched pair of subjects.

Table 4.1 Paired Samples Correlations

	Paired Samples Correlations	N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Expected & Perceived tangibles	10	.818	.000
Pair 2	Expected & Perceived Reliabilities	10	.367	.000
Pair 3	Expected & Perceived Responsiveness	10	.607	.000
Pair 4	Expected & Perceived Assurance	10	.737	.000
Pair 5	Expected & Perceived Empathy	10	.744	.003

Source: Authors Field Survey, January, 2011

At a correlation level of 0.818, 0.367, 0.607, 0.737, and 0.744 are the pair-wise correlation between expected tangible and perceived tangible, expected responsiveness and perceived responsiveness, expected assurance and perceived assurance as well as expected empathy and perceived empathy respectively. However, it was found that reliability pair-wise correlation was found to be not significant indicating that the service delivery service of reliability falls short. Measurements were a little higher overall, but the change was inconsistent across respondents. Several gave a higher measurement, but several others either did not change or increased their measurement. Unlike the tangible, responsiveness, assurance and empathy, all subjects change their mind for reliability of service quality and did so quite consistently by giving it a little lower.

Table 4.2 Paired Sample Test

		Paired Differences					
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Z	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pair 1	Exp Tang – Perc Tang	-1.32000	1.5487	.02460	-6.001	9	.000
Pair 2	Exp Relia – Perc Relia	1.03000	2.78234	.03452	-4.132	9	.000
Pair 3	Exp Resp- Perc Resp	-1.42000	2.01276	.15642	-5.123	9	.000
Pair 4	Exp Assu – Perc Assu	-0.85000	1.08054	.12343	-6.570	9	.000
Pair 5	Exp Emp. - Perc Emp.	-0.98000	1.45328	.01262	-6.001	9	.000

Source: Authors Field Survey, January, 2011

The Mean column in the paired-samples Z (t test) table shows the mean difference between tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy measurements for expectation and perceived, each of the variables shows a negative value indicating increase in their perceived service quality, with the exception of the reliability dimension which gives a positive value indicating a decline in service delivery of the Institution with respect to

that dimension, in other words, the reliability dimension falls below their expectation which gives a positive value.

The Std. Deviation column gives the standard deviation of the mean difference for each respondent from the mean value.

The Std. Error Mean column highlights the index of the variability one can expect in repeated random samples of the same number of respondents.

In view of the fact that the significance value for change in all is less than 0.05, it can be concluded that the average increase of 1.3200 points for tangible, 1.0300 decrease in points for reliability, 1.42 increased for responsiveness, 0.8500 increase for assurance and 0.9800 increase for empathy per respondents is not due to chance variation, and can be attributed to the quality of services they received per each working day. In summary, there exist differences in what the customers perceived and what their expectation about the services of the institution are concerned, the management of Takoradi Technical University must maintain and improve if possible, their tangibility, assurance, empathy and responsiveness. Nevertheless, the institution must take urgent measures to tactically tackle their reliability. Furthermore, since four of the service quality dimensions have a higher perceived quality than expected quality, it is clearly shown that, the customers are well satisfied with the quality of services they are offered, there by refusing to reject the hypothesis that, Quality service has an effect on customer satisfaction.

4.2 Gap Analysis

On the tangibility dimension it was evidently found that materials associated with services (such as pamphlets and library books) at the Takoradi Technical University are visually appealing. It was generally agreed that the institution needs the provision of internet facilities to support research at Takoradi Technical University, which means that students feel that the institution needs to acquire internet facilities such as e-library equipment to support research. Respondents expect the Institution to have quality level of approximately 3.24 however; respondents were of the view that Takoradi Technical University actually had quality level of approximately 4.56 on the tangibility dimension of the institutions. The tangible facilities of institution exceeded normal expectation by approximately 1.32 which shows that the tangibility dimension of the institution is far above what was expected leading to excited or delighted students. On the responsiveness dimension, it was found that the total criteria used for measuring responsiveness contributed in the awarding of 4.56 of service quality level with an increase of 1.42 of level of service quality as against 3.14 of the expected responsiveness of the institution.

The reliability dimension showed an expected service quality of 4.01 while the perceive service quality was 2.98, a reduction of 1.03 in service quality which indicates that the University fell short of its service quality dimensions leading to student dissatisfaction.

Also, on the assurance dimension, it was recorded that, the expected service quality was 3.65, while the perception recorded 4.5 with an increase of 0.85 and thus giving the assurance dimension higher service quality, indicating that expected level of service quality fell below perceived level of service quality leading to the delight or excitement of students.

Finally, on the empathy dimension, the expected service quality recorded was 3.02 while the perceived service quality was 4.00. This represent an increase of 0.98 in service quality delivery, thus leading to satisfied students. After comparing the differences between students' perceptions and expectations, the results have shown a positive score, as the student's perception exceeded their expectation. It was found that all the service quality dimensions scored higher service quality grades with the exception of reliability dimension which was graded consistently low. The results indicate that the majority of respondents expect tertiary institutions to deliver service that will exceed their expectations. The respondents rated tangibility and responsiveness highest, followed by assurance, and then empathy. Reliability was rated the least important expectation according to the respondents. The results show that students' perception of service quality at Takoradi Technical University

comes above their expectations, presenting a great challenge to the Technical University, to maintain or even improve such dimensions.

5.1 Conclusions

The results have shown that students' perceptions about the service they receive from the Technical University exceed their expectations. The service quality dimensions that showed the largest gaps proved to be tangibility and responsiveness. Management and staff need to focus their attention on these dimensions so that they can increase the service quality that they offer their students, thereby meeting or exceeding student expectation. However, irrespective of the higher grading of the service quality dimensions, there should be the need to tackle some of the criteria that falls below the expected mark.

5.2 Recommendations

1. The results of the research showed that some of the expectations of the students were low. In view of this, there's the need for management to have a listening ear to those who work directly with the students so as to implement that which the students need to meet their expectations.
2. Management is being encouraged to use the SERVQUAL model to measure its service quality as this will help identify the various dimensions of services and statements that have the strength and weaknesses in monitoring and improving the service quality of the institution.
3. It's also recommended that management makes a conscious effort to improve teaching and learning by making available modern teaching equipment such as PA systems, projectors, internet access to enable students and lecturers have electronic materials for teaching and learning. This will go a long way in meeting the expectations of the students in this regard.

REFERENCES

- i Anderson, J. & Narus, J. (1998). *Business marketing: Understand what customers value*. Harvard Business Review, Nov.-Dec., 53-65.
- ii Archambault, S. (2000). *Paired Samples T Test*. [Online] Wellesley College. Available from: <http://www.wellesley.edu/Psychology/Psych205/pairtttest.html> [Accessed 15th September, 2010]
- iii Ballantyne, D., Christopher, M., & Payne, A. (1995). *Improving the quality of services marketing: Service (Re) design is the critical link*. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 11, 7-24.
- iv Brennan, J & Shah, T. 2000. *Quality assessment and institutional change: Experiences from 14 countries*. *Higher Education*, 30(3):331-349.
- v Creswell, J. W., V. L. Plano Clark, M. Gutmann, and W. Hanson. (2003). *Advanced mixed methods research designs*, in: *Handbook on mixed methods in the behavioral and social sciences*, ed. A. Tashakkori and C. Teddlie, pp. 209–40. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- vi Cronin, J. & Taylor, S. (1992). *Measuring service quality: A re-examination and extension*. *Journal of Marketing*, 56, 55-67.
- vii Darlaston-Jones, D., Pike, L., Cohen, L., Young, A., Haunold, S. and Drew, N. (2003). *Are they being served? Student expectations of higher education*. *Issues in Educational Research*, Vol. 13, No.1, pp. 31-52.
- viii Gronroos, C. (2000). *Service management and marketing: A customer relationship management approach*. 2nd Edition. West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons
- ix Harvey, L. (2001). *Student Feedback: A report to the Higher Education Funding*. Birmingham, Centre for Research into Quality.
- x Ivankova, N. V., Creswell, J. W. and Sheldon L. S. (2006). *Using Mixed-Methods Sequential Explanatory Design: From Theory to Practice*. <http://www.sagepublications.com> (Accessed 15th September, 2010)
- xi Lovelock, C.H., & Wirtz, J. (2004) *Services Marketing*. 5th Edition. New Jersey: Prentice- Hall

- xii Mavondo, F., & Zaman, M. (2000). *Student satisfaction with tertiary institution and recommending it to prospective students*. ANZMAC 2000. *Proceedings of the Australia New Zealand Marketing Academy* (pp. 787-792). 28 November-1 December, Griffith University, Gold Coast, Australia.
- xiii Mc Coll, R., Callaghan, B and Palmer, A. (1996). *Services Marketing: a managerial perspective*. Boston: McGraw-Hill.
- xiv Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A., & Berry, L.L. (1988). *SERVQUAL: A multiple item scale for measuring customer perceptions of service quality*. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), 12-40.
- xv Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A., & Berry, L.L. (1985). *A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research*. *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 49, pp. 41-50.
- xvi Rossman, G. B. and Wilson, B. L. (1985). *Number and words: Combining quantitative and qualitative methods in a single large-scale evaluation study*. *Evaluation Review* Vol. 9 (5), pp. 627-43.
- xvii Wright, C. & O'Neill, M. (2002). *Service Quality Evaluation in the Higher Education Sector: An Empirical Investigation of Students' Perceptions*. *Higher Education Research & Development*, Vol.21 No. 1, 2002.
- xviii Zeithaml, V.A & Bitner M.J. (2003). *Services Marketing: Integrating customer focus across the firm*. 3rd Edition. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- xix Zeithaml, V., Rust, R., Lemon, K. (2001). *The customer pyramid: Creating and serving profitable customers*. *California Management Review*, 43 (4), 118-142.